

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4299371

Demographic and Institutional Factors Affecting Health Records Management Practice by Health Information Management Personnel in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of demographic and institutional factors on health records management practice among health information management personnel in selected hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. The descriptive survey design of correlational type was used for the study. The population of the study was made up of 95 health information management (HIM) personnel in the two selected hospitals. The total enumeration technique was adopted due to the manageable size of the population. The questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. The result showed that institution factors that affect health records management practice include access control, privacy, security and confidentiality policy, procedure and guidelines. Finally, the factors responsible for poor health records management practice include poor documentation and misfiling, mishandling of patient medical records by the users, insufficient professionally trained HIM personnel, insufficient filing space and unconducive office space. It is imperative that hospital management should address those predisposing institutional factors that affect records management practice, as well as train the existing ones to efficiently collect, preserve and promptly provide access to medical information to meet the needs of authorized users and other stakeholders in the health industry.

Keywords: Demographic factors, institutional factors, and health information management practice